

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin - INCREDIBLE

Grant Agreement number: 774632

Deliverable 2.1 – Compilation of co-developed ready-to-implement innovative knowledge

Coordination and Support Action H2020-RUR-2017-1: Thematic Networks compiling knowledge ready for practice

Start date of project: 1 November 2017

Duration of project: 36 months

Due date of deliverable: M35 (September 2020)

Actual submission date: M35 (September 2020)

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: CNPF

Type of Deliverable: Report

Dissemination level: Public

Authors: Benjamin Chapelet (CNPF), Joana Amaral Paulo (ISA), Eduard Mauri (EFI)

Coordinator

Partners

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774632

www.incredibleforest.net

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	3
1.1. Scope of this deliverable.....	3
1.2. Purpose of this document.....	3
2. Location of the collection and EIP-AGRI practice abstracts.....	3
3. Structure and content of the collection.....	4
3.1. Structure of the fact sheets	4
3.2. Distribution of the fact sheet production	6
3.3. Querying and browsing the fact sheets collection	7
4. Collecting the knowledge	7
5. The Knowledge contest.....	7
5.1. Selection of finalists	7
5.2. The Research-into-Action summary awards.....	9

Reference

Chapelet, B., Amaral Paulo, J. and Mauri, E. (2020) Compilation of co-developed ready-to-implement innovative knowledge - Deliverable 2.1. H2020 project no. 774632 RUR-2017-1 European Commission, 9 pp.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope of this deliverable

Deliverables 2.1 *Compilation of co-developed ready-to-implement innovative knowledge* aims at collecting relevant information on NWFPs innovations (research, success stories, best practices, databases, technical reports, policies, etc.). These pieces of information take the form of fact sheets and have been collected either from primary INCREDIBLE data, stemming from the collective knowledge of the consortium and screening of existing repositories, or from Secondary data from available and relevant scientific and grey literature. Moreover, in order to capture new ideas, but also to mobilize the broader community and to contribute to a mind-set change in relation to science-practice interaction, a Knowledge contest has been organized, awarding the best Research-into-Action summary from researchers and practitioners.

The target is to provide at least 250 fact sheets evenly spread across the five innovation networks (iNet): resins, cork, aromatic & medicinal plants, wild mushrooms & truffles and wild nuts & berries. Following EIP standards, this ready-to-use knowledge collection will feed into a knowledge repository (T2.3 and D2.2) and will be adapted and uploaded into the EIP-AGRI practice abstracts database.

1.2. Purpose of this document

This document aims at reporting:

- the location of the collection of fact sheets and EIP-AGRI practice abstracts (**chapter 2**),
- the structure and content of the collection of fact sheets (**chapter 3**),
- how Task 2.1 *Collection of knowledge from research and practice* has been conducted (**chapter 4**), and
- the current stage of the Knowledge contest (**chapter 5**).

2. Location of the collection and EIP-AGRI practice abstracts

The collection of knowledge is composed of 256 fact sheets hosted in the *Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products* website: <https://repository.incredibleforest.net/>

The collection of practice abstracts is hosted in the five *Project* pages, one per innovation network, of EIP-AGRI website. Because each project tab has a maximum of 100 practice abstracts, the collection has been split according to the five innovation networks. Each practice abstract has a link to its related fact sheet, where the reader can get more detailed information (see section 3.1).

- Resins: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/incredible-innovation-networks-cork-resins-and>
- Cork: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/incredible-innovation-networks-cork-resins-and-1>
- Aromatic & medicinal plants: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/incredible-innovation-networks-cork-resins-and-0>
- Wild mushrooms & truffles: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/incredible-innovation-networks-cork-resins-and-2>
- Wild nuts & berries: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/incredible-innovation-networks-cork-resins-and-3>

This ready-to-use knowledge collection has been compiled according to EIP standards by keeping the following three fields already integrated into the fact sheets:

- Title: in English and local language, maximum 150 characters,

- Main results: in English and local language, between 500 and 750 characters,
- Main practical recommendations: in English and local language, between 500 and 750 characters.

All the fact sheets and practice abstracts are published in English and also available in the national language of the publishing partner. Once the collection is completed, each partner will be allowed to select the fact sheets they would like to have translated in their own national language, as part of Task 4.3. *INCREDIBLE dissemination package*. Then the new translated versions will be published in the *Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products*.

3. Structure and content of the collection

3.1. Structure of the fact sheets

The structure of an INCREDIBLE fact sheet is designed to be unique and applicable to all five innovation networks plus a sixth category for fact sheets dealing with transversal topics. Here below are described all the fields composing a fact sheet (some private, for internal use only). The three specific fields also used for EIP-AGRI practice abstracts are indicated.

Themes & Questions: the fact sheets are classified according to 12 themes and 80 questions. Users can browse fact sheets by theme and question: <https://repository.incredibleforest.net/index.php/questions>.

Identification number (private field): a unique identification number is automatically assigned to each fact sheet, allowing the generation of one unique URL per fact sheet.

Non-wood forest products: one NWFP or more can be selected.

- Aromatic & Medicinal Plants
- Cork
- Resins
- Wild Mushrooms & Truffles
- Wild Nuts & Berries

Primary NWFP (private field): when more than one NWFP appear in the fact sheet, this field is used by rapporteurs to signal which is the most relevant NWFP concerned. If all NWFP present in the fact sheet have similar relevant, the fact sheet is classified as “transversal”.

Keywords: eight keywords maximum, the first four being common to all fact sheets of the same NWFP and the last four freely chosen by the rapporteur.

Type of fact sheet: classifies the source of the fact sheet information, whether it stems from:

- Research
- Practice

Position in the Value Chain: specifies the position in the value chain concerned by the information in the fact sheet.

- Forestry
- Harvesting
- Primary industry
- Secondary industry
- Marketing & Consumers
- Policy
- R&D

- Training and support decision tools

Type of data (private field): the fact sheet is issued from specific data or information.

- Scientific book
- Scientific article
- Practitioner article
- Technical documentation
- EU publication
- Project results
- Database
- Success story
- Good practice

Source (private field): the source of the fact sheet is indicated.

- Bibliographic review
- Personal communication outside Incredible events
- Personal communication in an Incredible events (interregional workshop)
- Personal communication in an Incredible events (science to practice)
- Personal communication in an Incredible events (cross-cutting seminar)
- Personal communication in an Incredible events (policy forum)

Scale: geographical scale of application of the innovation presented in the factsheet.

- Global
- Continental
- Sub-continental
- National
- Subnational
- Local

Figure 1 and credit: for decorative purposes, with credit in English and local language.

Figure 2, caption and credit: for explanatory purposes, with caption and credit in English and local language.

Location: a map with the most representative location of the fact sheet.

Scale: scale of applicability of the factsheet. Possible values (one ore many): Global, Continental, Subcontinental, National, Subnational, Local

Title (English and local language): to be included in **EIP-AGRI practice abstracts**. Short and easily understandable (one key sentence on the project; max 150 characters)

Context (English and local language): e.g. drivers or other causes that were at the origin. min 300 characters to max 600 characters.

Objective (English and local language): what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (min 300 characters to max 600 characters)

Main results (English and local language): to be included in EIP-AGRI practice abstracts (1st part of the practice abstract), between 500 and 750 characters.

Main practical recommendations (English and local language): to be included in EIP-AGRI practice abstracts (2nd part of the practice abstract), between 500 and 750 characters.

Impacts and weaknesses (English and local language): between 300 and 650 characters.

Future developments (English and local language): between 300 and 650 characters.

Further information: list of references (scientific or grey literature), links to films or websites, etc.

Author(s): the author is the main contact that provided the information of the fact sheet. It represents the person to who the reader should ask for more detailed first-hand information. It includes the name, the e-mail, the organisation, the country and the region.

Rapporteur: the rapporteur is the staff member of the INCREDIBLE consortium who uploaded and edited the fact sheet in the repository. Name, organisation and e-mail are provided.

3.2. Distribution of the fact sheet production

The **initial target number of 250 fact sheets** was distributed among partners according to the following rules, intended to be rationale and equitable:

- Even number of factsheets per Innovation network (= 50) for each of the 5 iNets.
- Even number of factsheets per partner involved in the iNet.

Among each partner's factsheets, we expected about 60% from Research and 40% from Practice. This was more a principle than a strict rule. Any change regarding this distribution was discussed among the innovation network partners and coordinators, and agreed with the task leaders.

A total of **256 factsheets have been finally published**. Depending on partners' implication in multiple innovations networks, and their level of expertise on the subject, the total number of fact sheets produced is different among partners (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of the 256 factsheets by INCREDIBLE partners and non-wood forest products.

Country	Partner	Aromatic & medicinal plants	Cork	Wild mushrooms & truffles	Wild nuts & berries	Resin	Trans-versal	Total
Croatia	CFRI	11		8				19
France	CNPF	8	6	8	6	10	1	39
Greece	UOI	8		8				16
Italy	ETIFOR			7	2		1	10
	FORESTAS		8					8
Portugal	UNAC		8		7			15
	ISA		11		11	6		28
Spain	INIA		8		9	8		25
	CTFC	11		9	0			20
	CESEFOR			9	7	10		26
Tunisia	INRGREF	27	5		10	5	3	50
Total		65	46	49	52	39	5	256
of which:	research	37	27	18	28	23	3	136
	practice	28	19	31	24	16	2	120

3.3. Querying and browsing the fact sheets collection

In the *Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products*, there is a search toolbox to querying the collection through text search, scale of applicability, non-wood forest products, types of fact sheet, position in the value chain, country of origin and keywords. In the same page, users can view the location of all the fact sheets on a map and select there the factsheets by location:

<https://repository.incredibleforest.net/oppla-factsheets>

Users can also browse the whole collection by themes and questions:

<https://repository.incredibleforest.net/questions>

4. Collecting the knowledge

The objective of 250 fact sheets was exceeded with a number of 256 fact sheets in the *Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products* by September 2020.

The best knowledge and practices have been collected by the INCREDIBLE consortium partners through the animation of the five innovation networks, with external contribution coming from the communities of practitioners and researchers. Ideas and subjects were also identified during the different events, such as Interregional workshops, Cross-cutting seminars and Science-to-practice events.

The process of writing is straightforward. Each rapporteur collects the information and uploads it in the repository database. Once completed, the rapporteur submits it on-line and the editor (the coordinator of the innovation network to which the fact sheet belongs) is automatically notified. Editors review the fact sheet and can request amendments. The rapporteur receives the comments, makes all the corrections requested and resubmits the factsheet. Editor is the responsible person to publish the fact sheet.

Once published, an HTML and a PDF version are automatically generated, following the established templates.

5. The Knowledge contest

5.1. Selection of finalists

The Knowledge contest was defined in the INCREDIBLE proposal in order to:

- Make knowledge “emerge” and capture it to generate fact sheets,
- Stimulate participation to the events,
- Provide a participatory activity for the INCREDIBLE events.

As described in the Task 2.1 p.13 of the DOA: *In addition, not only to be able to capture new ideas, but also to mobilise the broader community and to contribute to a mind-set change in relation to science-practice interaction, best Research-into-Action summary awards for researchers and practitioners will be launched as defined in cooperation with Task 4.1. A total of five awards will be*

launched on selected themes emerging from Task 2.2. Winners will be awarded with short scientific visits.

The Knowledge contest was launched in November 2019 to the INCREDIBLE partners who shared it among their innovation networks of practitioners and researchers. For better communication, any future event would also refer to this contest and encourage organisers to host an event-specific Knowledge contest to choose the best knowledge presented and encourage the author to write it in a fact sheet and become a finalist for the INCREDIBLE Knowledge contest. The contest was announced via partners' social media, communication channels and the INCREDIBLE website in the section *Open calls*¹. The INCREDIBLE Knowledge contest was also open to any external person outside the INCREDIBLE consortium who contributes to the *Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products* via the production of a factsheet in the role of author.

The first way to participate made two finalists to emerge (both from Interregional workshops), while the second way allowed project partners to select five finalists, one per innovation network. Currently, depending on the COVID-19 situation, this first number could increase if remaining INCREDIBLE events celebrate new event-specific knowledge contests, while the second number is fixed and the selection of the finalists is underway (Figure 1).

A common methodology has been shared among the partners to organize the selection of five finalists (one per innovation network) according an internal selection and an evaluation grid and the final winner.

Figure 1. General schema of the Knowledge contest process.

¹ <https://www.incredibleforest.net/fr/content/INCREDIBLE-knowledge-contest-nwfp>

5.2. The Research-into-Action summary awards

The seven finalists will be contacted and invited to attend the INCREDIBLE Final conference (or attend through videoconference) for the Research-into-Action summary awards ceremony. All INCREDIBLE partners may provide financial help for the seven finalists to attend the final conference. These seven finalists will compete at the same level for the award. They will present in three minutes their knowledge in a public session of the Final conference. Then the jury will vote (voting procedure and jury composition still to be defined) to select the winner.

The winner of the Research-into-Action summary awards will be awarded with a multi-day visit (to be taken within the 365 days following the Final conference) to the INCREDIBLE consortium partner organisation² of his/her interest (except ESSET). This visit will allow the winner to learn first-hand how the NWFP of his/her interest is managed across the value chain in a given region, and the state-of-the art in research. He/she will also be put in contact with local or regional stakeholders of the same NWFP. The cost of the award will be covered by the European Forest Institute through its *Short Term Mobility Grant* programme.

² <https://incredibleforest.net/partners>